

A case of vasculitic neuropathy: successful healing using yoga prana vidya (YPV) healing protocols as complementary medicine

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Abstract

Introduction: Vasculitic neuropathy is a condition in a patient when there is inflammation in the blood vessels supplying peripheral nerves, often causing both sensory and motor dysfunction, showing up as unusual sensations, numbness, pain and weakness of the muscles in the limbs. Usual medical treatment is to use Corticosteroids for a limited period, and recovery may take several months to years from case to case. Yoga Prana Vidya healing protocols were used as complementary medicine in the case presented in this paper to achieve speedy and effective recovery.

Method: This paper used case study method going through patient's medical records, healer's records and patient feedback.

Results: Patient started feeling relief in pain as healing started, and felt relaxed. There were no other noticeable side effects of medicines. The patient fully recovered within 6 months of YPV healing and further healings were discontinued.

Conclusions: The YPV healings enabled the patient complementary to the prescribed medication to recover from vasculitis condition physically and emotionally, and also reducing drug induced side effects. Further research is recommended. It will be beneficial to frontline health workers to acquire some working knowledge of YPV healing to complement their specialties to holistically heal the patients.

Keywords: Yoga Prana Vidya System ®; YPV®; Vasculitic neuropathy

1. Introduction

1.1. Vasculitic neuropathy

Vasculitic neuropathy is a condition in a patient when there is inflammation in the blood vessels supplying peripheral nerves, often causing both sensory and motor dysfunction, showing up as unusual sensations, numbness, pain and weakness of the muscles in the limbs. The inflammation may lead to constriction of blood vessels and subsequent reduced blood flow in the organs and tissues. The symptoms of Vasculitic neuropathy depend on the type and location of the nerve fibre involved. Symptoms generally include tingling sensation in hand fingers, swelling, stiffness and pain. Unlike many of the other peripheral neuropathies, vasculitic neuropathy may affect one limb more than the rest [1].

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They can be broadly classified as systemic vasculitic neuropathy (SVN) and nonSVN (NSVN). Diagnosis of Vasculitic neuropathy is based on history, clinical examination and supporting laboratory investigations. Treatment of Vasculitic neuropathies depends on controlling the underlying inflammation in the blood vessels. Since the underlying blood vessel inflammation is an autoimmune disorder, VN often responds to immunomodulatory therapies. Treatment with combined steroids and cyclophosphamide, azathioprine, or methotrexate is recommended if there is no response. Good outcomes have been reported in VN with adequate therapy in previous studies with 5-year survival rates up to 87% [2].

The use and impact of complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) associated with vasculitis has not been reported. A study by Berg et al (2014) on CAM for anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (ANCA) associated vasculitis (AAV), found that CAM practices were commonly used to improve well-being and found to be beneficial among AAV patients, but Berg et al. recommend more open discussion is needed about CAM between physicians and patients [3].

This study presents a case of Vasculitic Neuropathy of a 32-year-old woman patient treated with Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) healing protocols as complementary medicine in successfully healing this condition to become normal within 6 months.

1.2. Yoga Prana Vidya

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system of healing has been successfully applied to a wide range of illness conditions as complementary and as also as an alternative medicine, as is evident from over 60 published research papers [4]. YPV is an integrated and holistic system, which consists of physical and breathing exercises, forgiveness sadhana and meditation techniques, and bioplasmic (Pranic) energy healing techniques.

Literature shows some published successful case reports on applications of YPV that include, treatment of difficult medical cases [5], diabetes management & control [6], removing arterial block in heart without surgery [7], vision improvements for participants of an Eye Camp [8], improvements in holistic wellbeing and immunity of participants in a one-month YPV intensive programme [9], Role of Yoga Prana Vidya in first aid and emergency [10], speedy recovery of COVID patients [11], treatment of hypothyroidism [12], Lowering academic anxiety and enhancing academic performance of high school children [13], saving life of a snake-bitten human female [14], managing the pain and side effects of a Hodgkin Lymphoma patient undergoing chemotherapy [15], healing treatment of a female patient suffering from kneecap dislocation [16], Treatment and cure of PCOS condition [17], a case of breast cancer successfully treated [18], De-addiction cases [19], etc. A review of published literature shows some experimental studies also conducted with successful outcomes such as improvements in the wellbeing of prisoners [20], significant reduction in anxiety and depression in corporate employees [21], improvements in the cognitive abilities and social behaviour of mentally challenged children [22].

2. Case report

The patient is a female Ayurvedic doctor, aged 32, single, and a YPV trainer and healer resident in Karnataka.

2.1. Pre YPV-Medical Condition

Patient started experiencing tingling sensation in fingers of both hands from February 2022. Both hands (more in right hand) and fingers got affected due to small blood vessels got inflamed and because of that, blood supply to peripheral nerves got hampered. For diagnostic assessment, she visited her doctor, and after blood tests the results showed vitamin D and Vitamin B12 deficiency. Accordingly, the doctor prescribed supplements, and even after taking supplements symptoms were increasing. Along with tingling sensation, swelling and pain also developed. She visited a neurologist and an immunologist for further diagnosis. After other tests the condition was diagnosed as Vasculitic neuropathy, an auto immune condition. A lab test dated 8 March 2022 showed ANA (Antinuclear Antibody) positive. The doctor prescribed immunosuppressants (steroids, 60mg). According to the patient, the probable cause was episodes of frustration, as she used to face some pressures from family members in certain matters, that created undue stress and frustration for her. However, there were no other physical health related issues. The Total duration of medical treatment was 3- 1/2 months.

2.2. YPV intervention

Initially the patient was worried and stressed about the disease condition. But as she herself is a YPV healer, she contacted YPV ashram for healing and, as healing started, she felt relaxed and calm. Through YPV Ashram the patient was given Healing sessions.

As hands were affected, the patient became totally dependent on her elderly mother for her own daily routine needs. It was depressing for her. As the patient was not able to do her work by own and could not move fingers, it was very difficult for her to face people. However, as the patient was supported by family members in all aspects it helped her to face the situation. Simultaneously she was being treated by an Immunologist. The following YPV protocols were used in healing:

- Standard YPV Psychotherapy
- Deep thorough cleaning of all chakrams and affected parts
- Infection protocol
- Healing Protocol for Muscular skeleton System
- Miraculous Healing Technique and Regeneration Technique for fingers
- Healings were given to counter the side effect of medicine
- Patient was practicing Rhythmic Yogic Breathing 7-8 times a day
- Attending Divine healing sessions morning and Night
- Forgiveness, salt water bath, affirmations.

Healing was done 2 times a day for 2 1/2 months, and then onwards, once a day. The period of YPV intervention was from 19 March 2022 to 15 September 2022 (nearly 6 months).

2.3. Post YPV Healing Results

After 12 days of healing, the patient reported 50% overall improvement, with reduced swelling. But fingers became stiff and could not be bent. Doctor suggested to reduce the dose of steroid medication by half after 15 days. After another week of healing, stiffness and tingling session were reducing further with 75% overall improvement.

As dosage of medicine was getting reduced her symptoms got resurfaced. Stiffness and tightness of fingers increased slowly in palm and fingers, more in thumb, index and middle finger in right hand. As a probable side effect of medication, the patient missed her periods for four months. YPV healings resolved this and the patient resumed normal periods.

Patient started feeling relief in pain as healing started, and felt relaxed. There were no other noticeable side effect of medicines. The patient fully recovered within 6 months of YPV healing by Sep 2022 and requested to stop healings as she herself started healing. Since 9/7/22 medication was stopped by the patient.

2.4. Patient's Feedback

"...I have started experiencing tingling sensation in fingers of both hands 7 months back. For this I went to visit our family doctor, and after blood tests the findings showed deficiency of Vitamin D and Vitamin B12, for that doctor prescribed supplements, even after taking supplements symptoms were increasing. Along with tingling sensation, started developing swelling and pain in fingers of both hands. Again, after other tests the condition was diagnosed as Vasculitic neuropathy, an auto immune condition. So, the doctor prescribed immunosuppressants (steroids) 60mg. After taking steroids along with YPV healings symptoms got decreasing. After 1 month of medication, doctor started reducing the dosage. Now the condition is 95% better.

"I observed that after taking healings the symptoms started reducing in a faster rate, before I was little worried and stressed about the condition but because of healing I was calm and relaxed. Actually, in my condition I can say recovery is fast. And also, usually when taking steroids immunity will be less so repeated respiratory infection will be there but for me there were no such infections. Now I'm almost normal and doing my day-to-day activities smoothly on my own. Thank you for the healings."

3. Discussion

General recommendation for treatment of VN is to administer medication for 2-3 months or until clinical beneficial effect is noted, then taper gradually according to the patient's response. Otherwise, to continue treatment for 6 months to 1 year or longer. Some patients may require long-term immunosuppression for years [23]. In this case the medication was stopped after 3-1/2 months which show satisfactory treatment was achieved with usage of YPV healing protocols as complementary medicine.

It is further noted that YPV healing which is a CAM treatment using mind-based practices has been found effective in this case in speedy recovery, improving patient well-being, mind-body coordination, and eliminating anxiety and worry of the disease, which is in line with the findings of Berg et al. (2014) [3].

4. Conclusion

YPV healing practices have been found effective in the treatment and recovery process of Vasculitis Neuropathy case described in this study. As complementary and Alternative mode of treatment, YPV healing has been established as effective in the treatment of various types of illnesses and ill health conditions, and further research is recommended with appropriate methodology and sample size. It is worthwhile to impart a working knowledge of YPV system to frontline healthcare workers to complement their respective specialties.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

Not required for this study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from the patient.

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